

Adsorption of Ions by Sols of Aluminium Hydroxide and Vanadium Pentoxide.

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In two recent communications (*Koll-Zeit.*, 1927, **43**, 377; 1928, **45**, 12) M. N. Chakravarti and N. R. Dhar have deduced an absorption equation based on Langmuir's conception of residual valency, and have shown that this equation agrees satisfactorily with all their experimental results. Moreover the values of adsorption calculated from this equation are in much better agreement with the experimental results than the absorptions calculated from Freundlich's equation.

From the equation it follows that when the amount of adsorption is high, bivalent and trivalent ions are less absorbed than an univalent ion. On the other hand, when the amount of adsorption is small bi- and tri-valent ions are adsorbed more than an univalent ion. In order to test the foregoing conclusions we have carried on experiments on the adsorption of electrolytes by sols of aluminium hydroxide and vanadium pentoxide prepared in the cold.

In the adsorption of electrolytes by a sol of aluminium hydroxide or by freshly precipitated aluminium hydroxide there is great divergence among the results of different investigators. The following results were obtained by Gann (*Koll. Chem. Beihefte*, 1916, **8**, 63) with a sol of aluminium hydroxide of concentration of 2 gms. of Al_2O_3 per litre.

Anions.	Coagulating power.	Adsorption in millimoles per gm. of Al_2O_3 .
Salicylate	0·125	0·30
Picrate	0·250	0·18
Oxalate	2·770	0·18
Ferricyanide	10·000	0·09
Ferrocyanide	12·500	0·073

On the other hand the results obtained by Weiser and Middleton (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1920, **24**, 630) are different from those of Gann and are as follows:—

Anions.	Coagulating power.	Adsorption in millimoles per gram of Al_2O_3 .
Ferrocyanide	10.64	0.3202
Thiosulphate	5.32	0.4096
Ferricyanide	7.52	0.4046
Sulphate	3.75	0.4984
Oxalate	2.86	0.5710
Chromate	1.54	0.4352
Dithionate	1.23	0.3284
Dichromate	1.13	0.3185
Phosphate	2.80	0.8088

From the above results it is evident that in the majority of cases the greater the valency and hence the coagulating power of an ion and the less is its adsorption. It is evident from these results that aluminium hydroxide is a good adsorbent of different ions although Ishizaka has shown that grown alumina can adsorb ions only to the extent of 0.002 to 0.05 millimoles per gram of adsorbent. On the other hand Sen (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1927, **31**, 686) has obtained the following results in the adsorption of acids by freshly precipitated aluminium hydroxide.

Acids. Citric.	Oxalic.	Tartaric.	Sulphuric.
Adsorption in millimoles ...	0.783	0.952	0.933	0.896

From the above results it will be seen that the precipitated aluminium hydroxide has a very high adsorptive power.

We have carried on experiments on the adsorption of anions by a sol of aluminium hydroxide prepared in the cold. The sol was prepared by the repeated washing of a precipitate of aluminium hydroxide prepared at the ordinary temperature by the action of aluminium nitrate and ammonium hydroxide. When the precipitate of aluminium hydroxide is practically free from electrolytes, it passed into a stable sol. The concentration of the sol was 2.42 gms. of Al_2O_3 per litre. 20 C.c. of the sol were taken in well washed and dried stoppered bottles and 5 c.c. of N/10 solutions of different electrolytes added and the volume made up to 50 c.c. in each case. It was kept overnight and the anions unadsorbed estimated in the clear supernatant liquid. With each ion two such bottles were arranged and from the mean the adsorption in millimoles per gram

of Al_2O_3 calculated. The following results were obtained:—

Anions.	Adsorption in millimoles per gram of Al_2O_3 .
Bromate	1.4600
Chloride	1.3900
Iodate	1.3520
Dichromate	0.4964
Ferrocyanide	0.3595
Oxalate	0.1549

Thus we get the following order of adsorption, bromate being adsorbed the most and the oxalate the least:—

Bromate > Chloride > Iodate > Chromate > Ferrocyanide > Oxalate.
It is also found that the bromate ion possesses the least coagulating power of all the other monovalent ions.

From the following results it will be seen that all the univalent ions, chloride, bromate, and iodate are all highly adsorbed and the adsorption is greater than the adsorption of bi- and poly-valent ions. The adsorption of dichromate is less than that of the tetravalent ferrocyanide ion. It is difficult to explain the low adsorption of oxalate ion by a sol of aluminium hydroxide. Our experimental results conclusively prove that in general the smaller the valency of an ion the greater is the adsorption by a sol of aluminium hydroxide. These experimental results on the sol of aluminium hydroxide support our conclusions expressed in previous papers (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1924, 28, 457; 1926, 30, 628; 1927, 31, 997) that in general an ion which has a small valency and coagulating power for a colloid is most adsorbed by the colloid in question.

It will be observed from the foregoing tables that the adsorption of an ion by the sol, with which we made experiments, is appreciably greater than the adsorption obtained by Gann, and Weiser and Middleton. This difference is certainly due to the following reasons:—It has been repeatedly observed that the adsorptive power and chemical reactivity of a substance become less when the substance is heated. Weiser and Middleton prepared their sol of aluminium hydroxide in boiling water, consequently the sol became aged and lost chemical reactivity and the power of adsorption appreciably. Our sol was not heated at all. It was prepared in the cold and washed also with cold water and consequently it did not age and did not lose its chemical reactivity and the adsorptive power of our sol was greater than those prepared by the workers. From the results of Sen it will be seen that he

obtained very high adsorption with freshly precipitated aluminium hydroxide. This is mainly due to the fact that Sen prepared his aluminium hydroxide in the cold. Moreover M. N. Chakravarti and N. R. Dhar (*loc. cit.*) obtained the fairly high adsorption of anions with a freshly precipitated sample of aluminium hydroxide prepared in the cold.

Adsorption experiments were also carried on with vanadium pentoxide sol. which was prepared according to the method of Biltz. Three grams of ammonium vanadate were made into a paste with water and 22 c. c. of 10 per cent. HCl added. A red precipitate of vanadium pentoxide is formed. The precipitate was freed from the mother-liquor by continual washing, and when free from ammonium chloride and added HCl, it begins to pass into the colloidal state. On adding 500 c. c. of water to the precipitate it passed into a red colloid, which was dialysed for eight days till the outside water was free from electrolytes.

The sol was estimated by evaporating to dryness on a platinum crucible over water-bath and then igniting and weighing it as V_2O_5 . It contained 1.41 grams of V_2O_5 per litre. This sol was found to be negatively charged.

On coagulating the sol with different electrolytes a major portion of the sol was precipitated and only a small portion remained in solution which was estimated in each case by reducing it with sulphurous acid and titrating the vanadyl salt thus produced with standard potassium permanganate.

20 C. c. of the sol were taken in stoppered bottles and 5 c. c. of M/10 solutions of different electrolytes added. The volume was made up to 50 c. c. in each case. The filtrate was evaporated to dryness in a platinum crucible over water-bath and weighed.

The following results were obtained :—

Electrolytes.	Total original before adsorption in 50 c. c. of the mixture.	Total adsorption in 50 c. c. and V_2O_5 .	Amount of V_2O_5 in 50 c. c.	Adsorption in 50 c. c.	Gram mole adsorbed per gm. of V_2O_5 .
KCl (estimated as K_2SO_4).	0.0845	0.07225	0.0075	0.01975	0.00804
$BaCl_2$ (estimated as $BaSO_4$).	0.2320	0.2275	0.0056	0.0101	0.00153
$Al(NO_3)_3$ (estimated as Al_2O_3).	0.0505	0.05875	0.0135	0.00525	0.00364
$Th(NO_3)_4$ (estimated as ThO_2).	0.3380	0.31075	Nil.	0.02735	0.00368

When vanadium pentoxide sol was precipitated with $\text{Th}(\text{NO}_3)_4$, it sets to a stiff jelly and hence the determination of the amount of adsorption has to be carried on with great difficulty. From the above results it will be seen that the univalent potassium ion is more adsorbed than the bivalent or polyvalent ions. There is some uncertainty regarding the adsorption of aluminium and thorium salts because of the marked hydrolysis of these substances.

It is also very interesting to note in this connection that the amount of vanadic acid remaining in solution after precipitation of the colloidal portion is greatest when coagulated with aluminium nitrate, and then comes KCl, and then barium chloride and finally thorium nitrate in which case no trace of vanadic acid could be detected in the filtrate. It appears that thorium vanadate is very sparingly soluble.

Summary.

(1) The adsorptions of bromate, chloride, iodate, dichromate, ferrocyanide and oxalate ions by a sol of aluminium hydroxide prepared in the cold have been determined.

(2) The adsorptions of potassium, barium, aluminium and thorium ions by a dialysed sol of vanadium pentoxide have been measured.

(3) The experimental results show that an univalent ion is adsorbed more than a bivalent and a trivalent ion with both these sols.

(4) These results are in agreement with the deductions from the adsorption equation of the authors.

